

NOTES

Studies on Hydroxamic Acids. Part V. Preparation and Properties of *N*-Arylhydroxamic Acids

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In a recent communication¹ a procedure, based on Schotten-Baumann reaction, was described for the preparation of *N*-arylhydroxamic acids. The same procedure has been successfully adapted here for preparing 13 more new *N*-arylhydroxamic acids derived from substituted acetic acid and long chain aliphatic carboxylic acids. Thus, freshly prepared *N*-arylhydroxylamine and vacuum distilled acid chloride in equimolar proportions are reacted at low temperature in diethyl ether containing aqueous suspensions of sodium bicarbonate. The *N*-arylhydroxamic acids so obtained are purified by crystallization from a mixture of either benzene and petroleum ether or ethyl alcohol and water.

A typical preparation of *N*-arylhydroxamic acid is described below.

N-Phenyl 2,4,5-trichlorophenoxyacetoxyhydroxamic acid.

In a 500-ml. filtration flask fitted with a dropping funnel by a B-24 joint, 75 ml. of diethyl ether, 1.09 g. (0.01 mole) of freshly purified *N*-phenylhydroxylamine, and a fine suspension of 1.64 g. (0.02 mole) sodium bicarbonate in 10–15 ml. of water were taken and stirred with a magnetic stirrer. After the mixture was externally cooled to 0° or lower, 2.74 g. (0.01 mole) of solid 2,4,5-trichlorophenoxyacetyl chloride dissolved in 75 ml. of diethyl ether were added to it dropwise over a period of 1 hr. Then the reaction mixture was stirred for an additional 30 min. and the temperature kept low to prevent the possible side reactions. Almost the entire amount of hydroxamic acid was precipitated as a white granular solid. The light yellow ethereal layer on separation and distillation under vacuum left negligible amount of a yellow solid, which was discarded. The precipitated white product was triturated with a saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate in a glass mortar for about 15 min. to remove acidic impurities. It was then filtered off, washed with cold water, and dried under folds of filter paper, m.p. 180°. On one crystallization from a mixture of ethyl

1. V. K. Gupta and S. C. Tandon, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 5 In Press,

TABLE I
 Properties of *N*-aryldihydroxamic acids

Compd. No.	Hydroxamic acid	Molecular formula	m.p.	% Yield	IR spectra			UV spectra in Et-OH			Analysis ^a %		
					ν O-H	ν C=O	ν N-O	λ_{\max} μ	$10^{-3}\epsilon$	$\frac{\lambda_{II}}{\lambda_I}$	C	H	N
I	<i>N</i> - <i>m</i> -Tolylmyristol	$C_{21}H_{35}NO_2$	71	60	3180	1630	921	208	29.2	1.21	75.55 (75.63)	10.73 (40.58)	4.29 (4.20) ^c
II	<i>N</i> - <i>m</i> -Tolylpalmito-	$C_{23}H_{39}NO_2$	74	60	3180	1630	921	208	15.0	1.23	76.35 (76.39)	10.99 (10.87)	3.67 (3.87)
III	<i>N</i> -Phenylstearo-	$C_{24}H_{41}NO_2$	87	65	3145	1626	907	208	19.8	1.22	76.60 (76.76)	11.07 (11.01)	3.93 (3.73)
IV	<i>N</i> - <i>m</i> -Tolylstearo-	$C_{25}H_{43}NO_2$	78	60	3175	1630	921	208	16.2	1.23	77.38 (77.07)	11.05 (11.13)	3.90 (3.59)
V	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Tolylstearo-	$C_{25}H_{43}NO_2$	84	60	3145	1613	909	208	12.0	1.20	77.61 (77.07)	11.13 (11.13)	3.65 (3.59)
VI	<i>N</i> -Phenylbehe-	$C_{26}H_{49}NO_2$	100	70	3175	1634	909	208	16.4	1.23	77.89 (77.90)	11.41 (11.44)	3.24 (3.24)
VII	<i>N</i> - <i>m</i> -Tolylbehe-	$C_{28}H_{51}NO_2$	86	58	3077	1613	909	208	19.5	1.23	78.30 (78.14)	11.63 (11.53)	— (3.14)
VIII	<i>N</i> - <i>m</i> -Tolylphenoxyaceto-	$C_{18}H_{16}NO_3$	130	63	3250*	1635	935	—	—	—	70.18 (70.02)	5.90 (5.88)	5.79 (5.45)
IX	<i>N</i> - <i>m</i> -Tolyl- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenoxyaceto-	$C_{16}H_{14}NO_3Cl$	189	65	3270*	1625	910	208	17.8	1.23	— (61.78)	4.62 (4.84)	4.97 ^b (4.80)
X	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenoxyaceto-	$C_{15}H_{14}NO_3Cl$	185	65	3280*	1620	915	208	16.9	1.22	61.69 (61.76)	5.06 (4.84)	4.88 ^c (4.80)
XI	<i>N</i> -Phenyl-2,4,5-trichlorophenoxyaceto-	$C_{14}H_{10}NO_3Cl_3$	184	60	3175	1639	913	208	26.1	1.21	48.24 (48.52)	2.92 (2.94)	3.81 (4.04)
XII	<i>N</i> - <i>m</i> -Tolyl-2,4,5-trichlorophenoxyaceto-	$C_{15}H_{12}NO_3Cl_3$	172	55	3125	1613	909	290sh 300sh	33.1	1.21	49.92 (49.95)	3.35 (3.35)	3.90 (3.88)
XIII	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Tolyl-2,4,5-trichlorophenoxyaceto-	$C_{15}H_{12}NO_3Cl_3$	190	60	3125	1639	909	208	33.3	1.22	49.77 (49.95)	3.67 (3.35)	3.58 (3.88)

^a Calculated values are given in parentheses.

^b calcd : Cl, 12.15 Found : Cl, 12.12

^c calcd : Cl, 12.15 Found : Cl, 11.96

* on Perkin Elmer Model 221 as KBr pellets. Rest are on Perkin Elmer 137 as nujol mulls.
sh inflection (shoulder).

alcohol and water (without the use of charcoal) long white needles were obtained; yield 2.1 g., 60% of the theoretical, m.p. 184°. Two crystallizations gave a product which was excellent for analytical work.

All the hydroxamic acids could be prepared by following the above procedure.

DISCUSSION

The physical properties of *N*-arylhydroxamic acids are given in Table I. All of the hydroxamic acids are white crystalline solids. These are stable to heat, light and air. They are sparingly soluble in water but are readily soluble in ethyl alcohol, benzene, chloroform, diethyl ether and dioxane. Hydroxamic acids derived from phenoxy acetic acids (compounds VIII to XIII) have relatively poor solubilities in benzene, diethyl ether and chloroform.

The infrared and ultraviolet spectra of the synthesised hydroxamic acids were determined primarily for their characterisation. In the infrared spectra the considerable shift of hydroxy and carbonyl bands to lower frequencies is ascribed to intramolecular hydrogen bonding in these acids. This is further confirmed by studies made in chloroform solutions.

In the ultraviolet region there are two characteristic intense bands around 208 and 255 $m\mu$ which are assigned as benzene bands^{2,3} I (secondary primary) and II (first primary), respectively.

The assignment of bands is logical and is supported by the evidence which follows. It is recognised through the work of Doub and Vandenberg³ that in mono and disubstituted benzene derivatives the benzene bands register considerable shift to longer wavelengths. The ratio of wavelengths of bands II and I, λ_{II}/λ_I , is generally found to be 1.25 and is useful for discriminating these bands. In all the hydroxamic acids recorded here this ratio is around 1.23 and suggests benzenoid absorption. The magnitude of intensity of these bands confirms this conclusion. Besides, this viewpoint is further corroborated by the previous work from this laboratory⁴ on 22 analogous hydroxamic acids derived from aliphatic carboxylic acids, where the two bands at $207 \pm 1 m\mu$ and $248 \pm 2 m\mu$ were designated as benzene bands I and II respectively. It may be noted that the length of the aliphatic chain and the nature of substituents have little effect on the position of these bands.

All of the hydroxamic acids react with vanadium(V) in concentrated hydrochloric acid (2 to 10*M*) media and the reaction products on extraction with chloroform give characteristic violet extracts. Solvent extraction behaviour and analytical potentialities of these violet reaction products are under study.

2. P. Bladon, "Ultraviolet and Visible Spectroscopy", ed. J. C. P. Schwarz, "Physical Methods in Organic Chemistry." Oliver and Boyd, London, 1967, p. 146.
3. L. Doub and J. M. Vandenberg, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 2714; 1949, **71**, 2414. *ibid*,
4. V. K. Gupta, *Ph.D. Thesis*, Univ. of Jabalpur, Jabalpur, 1969.

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